

THE ROLE OF END-TO-END ANALYTICS IN DIGITAL MARKETING

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РОЛЬ END-TO-END АНАЛИТИКИ В ЦИФРОВОМ МАРКЕТИНГЕ

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RAQAMLI MARKETINGDA END-TO-END TAHLILNING ROLI

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abstract

In our current scientific research, information is provided about the characteristics, types, advantages and components of digital marketing and why it cannot be effective without end-to-end analytics.

аннотация

В нашем текущем научном исследовании представлена информация о характеристиках, типах, преимуществах и компонентах цифрового маркетинга и о том, почему он не может быть эффективным без end-to-end аналитики.

annotatsiya

Bizning hozirgi ilmiy tadqiqotlarimizda raqamli marketingning xususiyatlari, turlari, afzalliklari va tarkibiy qismlari va nima uchun u oxirigacha tahlil qilmasdan samarali bo'lishi mumkin emasligi haqida ma'lumot berilgan.

Keywords:

digital marketing, influencer, brand development, internet platforms, mobile technologies, end-to-end analytics, SMM, UGS, SEO, SEM, context marketing.

Ключевые слова:

цифровой маркетинг, инфлюенсер, развитие бренда, интернет-платформы, мобильные технологии, сквозная аналитика, SMM, UGS, SEO, SEM-оптимизация, контекстный маркетинг.

Kalit so'zlar:

raqamli marketing, influencer, brendni rivojlantirish, internet platformalari, mobil texnologiyalar, end-to-end analytics, SMM, UGS, SEO, SEM, kontekst marketing.

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Digital marketing (digital marketing) is a form of marketing that uses digital technologies and internet platforms to improve and accelerate sales of products or services.

The main tasks of digital marketing are to develop the brand and increase sales using various methods. Digital marketing includes a wide range of marketing tactics for promoting goods, services and brands. Digital marketing methods use the Internet as the main means of communication in addition to mobile technology, traditional television and radio.

Key activities of digital marketing:

- 1) search engine optimization (SEO);
- 2) search marketing (SEM);
- 3) content marketing;
- 4) user content (UGS);
- 5) influencer marketing;
- 6) automation of content creation, e-commerce marketing;
- 7) social media marketing (SMM);
- 8) direct mail, contextual advertising, e-book advertisements;
- 9) programs, games and other forms of digital products;
- 10) Channels that are not directly connected to the Internet are also used: mobile phones (SMS and MMS), call back, call hold tones.

The core concept of digital marketing is a customer-centric approach. So, in short, digital marketing is a set of methods that use digital channels to advertise and sell goods and services. Now let's briefly touch on the 10 types of digital marketing activities listed above:

1. Search engine optimization (SEO) (advertisement of sites) - information of users for the purpose of increasing network traffic (for information resources), potential customers (for commercial resources) and subsequent monetization (earning) a set of internal and external optimization measures to raise the site's position in search engine results for lum queries.this traffic. SEO can be targeted to a variety of search engines, including information, goods, services, images, videos, news, addresses, contacts, and industry-specific search engines. Usually, the higher the position of the site in the search results, the more people who are interested in it will pass through the search engines.

2. Search engine marketing (SEM) is a set of activities aimed at increasing site traffic by the target audience using search engines. Search marketing methods include all methods that solve this problem, from attracting targeted traffic directly from off-site links to on-site work, the site's own TA (target audience) (thus increasing the visibility of the site in search engines by reranking the search results in favor of this site for key queries).

3. Content marketing is a set of marketing techniques based on creating and/or distributing useful information for consumers to gain trust and attract potential customers. Content marketing involves the preparation and distribution of high-quality, relevant and valuable information that is not directly advertising, but indirectly persuades the audience to make the decision needed by the distributor. Examples of

such information: the general situation in a certain market segment, events in it, methods of solving problems related to this segment, including how the distributor's products or services help to solve these problems.

4. UGC (User Generated Content) or user content is material about a brand created by ordinary people and made public. UGC includes comments, videos, photos, reviews. Companies are using user content in their marketing strategies. With its help, you can promote the product locally, attract the audience to interact with the brand, and also increase your appeal.

5. Influence Marketing is the promotion of products or services through Influencers or opinion leaders. An influencer is not only a well-known person, but also a blogger, an expert in his field, a person who manages social networks and is well-known in a certain field. You don't have to have a million followers to be an influencer. The effectiveness of influencer marketing does not depend on the number of subscribers, it is important to attract the audience to influential content (quality content). Nowadays, most people trust small bloggers with 3k followers more than big bloggers because they run their own camaraderie blogs.

According to the number of viewers, Influencers are divided into several groups:

- nanoinfluencers - up to 1000 subscribers;
- micro-influencers - from 5000 to 100 thousand subscribers;
- mid-influencers - from 100 thousand to 1 million;
- macroinfluencers - more than 1 million subscribers.

6. Automate content creation, e-commerce marketing is running a business using online channels, which are becoming the main way to attract and communicate with customers. Generally, e-commerce refers to the sale of goods and services over the Internet.

7. Marketing in social networks (Social media marketing, SMM) is marketing integrated into various social platforms (Telegram, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, TikTok, Vkontakte, etc.). Maintaining social media accounts is part of the marketing and communication strategy.

8. Direct mail is when you visit the Internet, you are interested in the information you need and leave a trace (IP address, account mail address). Companies that have found out about your demand will send their product offer to your mail. Contextual advertising is a type of Internet advertising, in which advertising is displayed according to the content, place, time or other context of Internet pages selected by the audience (Latin contextus - connection, connection).

9. Various companies place their advertisements and find their customers in the programs, games and other forms of digital products that you download to your smartphone or PC.

10. In this type of digital marketing, companies send direct information about their products via SMS or MMS.

End-to-end analytics is a way to help companies understand how their customers interact with them from start to finish. It allows you to combine and analyze data from various sources, such as online advertising and customer data, to make better advertising and service decisions.

Why end-to-end analytics?

End-to-end Analytics is a data collection method in marketing that helps track each customer's journey from their first encounter with a product to their purchase. It helps to understand from which sources (channels) customers come. So if we find a buyer, we can sell our product.

In our upcoming scientific articles, we will introduce each of the above 10 digital marketing activities in detail.

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